

Distribution of fish and their diversity index along a salinity gradient in the Lake Oloiden and the Lake Naivasha

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Abstract

An increase in the water level occurred in Lake Naivasha which lead to its merging with Lake Oloiden. This resulted to an estuarine environment. This occurrence may lead salinization of Lake Naivasha may have an impact in the fish distribution and diversity. The study was conducted monthly in the 7 study sites along a salinity gradient, for one year; salinity was measured using YSI Multiparameter meter and fish were caught using gill nets. Main aim of the study was to determine spatial diversity and distribution of fish along a salinity gradient in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden. Oloiden ST1, Oloiden ST2 and the other sites were distinct; a slight increase in salinity was noted at Oloiden ST2 before a drop (Oloiden ST2: Oseria was 3.5:1). Lake Oloiden (310±65 ppm) had a higher salinity as compared to the Lake Naivasha (96±20 ppm). A total of 10 fish species were caught and they belonged to: *Cichlidae*, *Centrarchidae*, *Cyprinidae* and *Clarridae*. *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio* and *Clarius gariepinus* and contributed the largest percentages in the catch: 65.3, 16.8 and 12 respectively. Malewa had the highest fish diversity index ($H'=0.46$) while the lowest was in the Midlake (0.17). Species evenness was highest in Malewa and lowest in Korongo. The Crescent had the highest species richness ($d=2.8$) while Midlake's was the lowest (0.5). Diversity index and evenness were low while species richness was high. There was a variation in the diversity and distribution of fish along the salinity gradient and fish of commercial importance migrated to Lake Oloiden post its merging with Lake Naivasha. Fish species diversity and evenness were low while species richness was high. Further research on the fish species diversity along the salinity gradient is recommended due to changes that may occur in biotic and abiotic factors with respect to time.

Key words: Diversity indices, *Cichlidae*, *Clarridae*, *Cyprinidae*

1.0 Introduction

There has been alternate reduction/increment in the surface area of the Lake Naivasha due to water level changes. The water level occurred 8-10 years ago due to increased discharge from the catchment that was associated with climate change (Nyangau 2021). A global increase in surface temperature occurred by 0.6 °C ; thus there has been climate change (Ndungu *et al.* 2014). The Lake Naivasha is fed by River Malewa, Gilgil and Karati, has underground seepage and evapotranspiration (Ballot *et al.*, 2009; Ndungu, 2014). Lake Oloiden is a bay on the southern part of the Lake Naivasha was separated by a papyrus reef (Ballot *et al.* 2009; Mironga *et al.* 2014). Lake Oloiden's hydrology is closed; maintained by rainfall, evaporation and subsurface inflow from Lake Naivasha (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). That which occurs in one impact the other lake: they connected during high-water level; their merging may have an effect on the aquatic organism's distribution due to their salinity differences (Ballot *et al.* 2009). Similarities of the fluctuations in the water level have been observed in the Lake Victoria and Lake Turkana (Nyangau 2021).

A tropical lake could have extreme lake level fluctuations. Water level changes in an aquatic environment should be considered in the assessment of the environmental impact (Obegi *et al.* 2021). The fluctuations in the level of the lake could be seen as a disturbance to an aquatic ecosystem but it maintains temporal and spatial heterogeneity for fish and other aquatic organisms. Fluctuations in the lake level is an essential disturbance in the environment (Nyangau 2021). All changes: salinity, water level, temperature may have an influence on residential and ecological community (D'alelio 2022). Many of physical, chemical and biological factors influence occurrence, distribution and abundance directly (Albaret *et al.* 2004).

Biodiversity has a positive relationship with the well-being of the species structure. An increase in the salinity may have a negative effect on the biodiversity; affecting fish diversity and distribution. An increase in salinity may negatively affect biodiversity: distribution and diversity; may negatively affect fish spawning. Salinity has been threatening the ecological sustainability of the south west Coastal region of Bangladesh. Paikgacha had a higher salinity as compared to Rampal. The number of fish being caught has been gradually decreasing. Salinity was stated as the factor responsible for the change in fisheries. A reduction in biodiversity may lead to a

decrease in production (some species may be extinct) and thus creating socio-economic instability (Gain *et al.* 2008).

The Lake Oloiden has not been having fish of commercial importance and its union with Lake Naivasha; may lead to salinization of the later; affecting fish diversity and distribution. The objective was to determining spatial diversity and distribution of fish along a salinity gradient in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study was done in the Lake Oloiden and Lake Naivasha: 00o50'S, 36o17'E and 00o46'S, 36o22E respectively (Ballot *et al.* 2009). It was undertaken along a transect featuring the salinity gradient (Oloiden ST1- Malewa) with an addition of two fish breeding sites in the Lake Naivasha (**Figure 1**). On the southern part of Lake Naivasha was Oloiden ST1. Oloiden ST2 was the second site, its shallow and borders Oseria site (ST3). The sites (ST2 and ST3) usually disconnect and connect in low and high-water level in the Lake Naivasha respectively allowing fresh water to mix with saline water resulting to an estuarine environment. Site four (ST4) was Crescent; a crater lake on the eastern part of Lake Naivasha that was connected to the main lake during high water levels. The sites 5 (ST5) was Korongo: a lagoon situated at the North-West that's connected to the main lake. Midlake was the sixth (ST6) and it's an open water site. Malewa was the seventh site (ST7); a swampy area in the north that was covered at the edge by *Pontederia crassipes* and *Cyperus papyrus*; where River Malewa drains into Lake Naivasha.

Figure 1. A study area map illustrating the sampling sites in the Lakes Oloiden and Naivasha respectively (Openstreetmap.org. 2021)

2.2 Salinity

The measurements were done once each month for one year (August, 2020 to July, 2021). Site respective measurements of salinity were done using YSI Multiparameter probe.

2.3 Fish

In each sampling station a pair: monofilament and a multifilament gill net (mesh 1.78-6 inches) were cast along a Global Positioning System (GPS) determined point for 4-6 hours during the day/ overnight. The fish nets were retrieved from the water, sorted according to the species (identification as per key by Keyombe *et al.*, 2017) and counted (Nyangau 2021).

2.3 Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) was used for analysis of salinity using: one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Tukey pairwise comparison was the post hoc. Analysis of diversity and distribution was done in R (4.3.1) using indices. The diversity, evenness and species richness were computed by the Shannon-Weiner index (H'), Shannon-Wiener evenness (E) and Margalef's index (d) (Margalef, 1958; Shannon and Wiener, 1963). The formulars are as listed below;

$$H' = \sum_i P_i \ln P_i \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

$$E = \frac{H}{\ln S} \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

$$d = \frac{S-1}{\ln(N)} \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

Where; $P=n/N$, \ln =natural logarithm, S =total number of species and N =number of individuals.

3.0 Results

3.1 Spatial variation in salinity

The salinity in the respective study sites was significantly different ($P<0.05$) and the Lake Oloiden's was higher (310 ± 65 ppm) compared to Lake Naivasha (96 ± 20 ppm) (**Figure 2**). The salinity in Oloiden ST2 was slightly increased compared to that of Oloiden ST1 before a decrease at Oseria. The ratio of Oseria's salinity to Oloiden ST2 was 1:3.5.

Figure 2. The salinity in the respective sites of the Lakes Oloiden and Naivasha.

3.2 Spatial variability in fish and abundance

Fish species (10 species) that were caught in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden belonged to 4 families (**Table 1**). The *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Cyprinus carpio* were found in all sites and their percentages in the catch were high. Oloiden ST1 and ST2 had the species; *Cyprinus carpio*, *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio specularis*, *Clarius gariepinus* and *Clarius aepithecus*. The *Oreochromis niloticus* was highly abundant overall (65.3%).

Table 1. The fish species and respective family in the various sites in the Lake Naivasha and Lake Oloiden and their abundance and percentage

Fish family and specie	Oloiden	ST1	Oloiden	ST2	Oseria	Crescent	Korongo	Midlake	Malewa	Abundance	%
<i>Cichlidae</i>											
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	761	65.3
<i>Oreochromis leucostictus</i>					X				X	31	2.66
<i>Coptodon zillii</i> (Gervais, 1848)						X				2	0.085
<i>Centrarchidae</i>											
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i>					X	X				13	1.12
<i>Cyprinidae</i>											
<i>Barbus amphigramma</i>						X				4	0.34
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	196	16.8
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> var. (Leather carp)									X	10	0.86
<i>Cyprinus carpio specularis</i> (mirror carp)	X						X		X	4	0.34
<i>Clarridae</i>											
<i>Clarius gariepinus</i>	X		X	X		X	X		X	143	12.3
<i>Clarius aepithecus</i>	X								X	2	0.17

Oreochromis niloticus contributed the largest percentage in all the sites in the study sites (**Table 2**). *Barbus amphigramma* and *Coptodon zillii* (Gervais, 1848) were present only in Crescent and their percentage contributions towards the catch were low. The specie *Micropterus salmoides* was present in low percentages at the Crescent and Oseria. *Cyprinus carpio* was present in all the sites, its percentage was varied throughout the sites: Oseria had the highest percentage and Oloiden ST2 had the lowest. The leather carp was only present in Malewa (low percentage) while the mirror carp was present in Oloiden ST1, Korongo and the Midlake. *Clarius gariepinus* was present in moderate percentages in Oloiden ST1, Oloiden ST2, Crescent and Malewa (highest) while *Clarius aepithecus* was present in Oloiden ST1 and Malewa.

Table 2. Composition of the fish species caught in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden study sites

Fish species	Study sites and % Composition						
	Oloiden ST1	Oloiden ST2	Oseria	Crescent	Korongo	Midlake	Malewa
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	76.4	87.2	66	73.3	75.2	85	50
<i>O. leucostictus</i>			0.34				4.5
<i>Coptodon zillii</i> (Gervais, 1848)				0.29			
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i>			0.34	2.03			
<i>Barbus amphigramma</i>				0.58			
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	4.7	2.8	21.9	9.3	11.7	15	21
<i>C. carpio</i> var. (Leather carp)							0.8
<i>C. carpio specularis</i> (mirror carp)	2.8				0.73	0.8	
<i>Clarius gariepinus</i>	13.9	11.1		14.53			21
<i>C. aepithecus</i>	2.8						1.5

3.2 Diversity indices

The overall Shannon-Wiener index was 0.33 ± 0.11 (**Figure 3**). It was highest in Malewa while the lowest was in the Midlake. Oloiden ST1's was higher as compared to Oloiden ST2 while Oseria's diversity index was higher as compared to Oloiden ST2.

Figure 3. The Shannon-Wiener index for fish in the Lakes Oloiden and Naivasha study sites

Overall, fish species evenness was 0.5 ± 0.1 . It was highest in Malewa, followed by the Midlake and then Oseria (**Figure 4**). Oloiden ST1 and ST2 had similar evenness and Oloiden ST2 was lower as compared to Oseria.

Figure 4. The Shannon-Wiener evenness for fish in the Lake Naivasha and Lake Oloiden study sites

The fish species richness was 1.52 ± 0.71 (overall). It was highest in Crescent and lowest in the Midlake (**Figure 5**). Oloiden ST1's was higher as compared to Oloiden ST2.

Figure 5. The Margalef's index for fish in the Lake Naivasha and Lake Oloiden study sites

4.0 Discussion

The salinity was higher in Oloiden ST1 and ST2 as compared to Lake Naivasha study sites (Hubble and Harper 2002; Ballot *et al.* 2009). Saline water and freshwater mix at Oloiden ST2 and Oseria; resulting in a salinity ration of 3.5: 1 respectively and thus, the salinity gradient. There was a slight increment in salinity at Oloiden ST2; which could be associated with non-linear variation in a brackish environment (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). An estuarine environment has an effect on the fish community (Albaret *et al.* 2004). Salinity is a major factor governing the distribution of fish. Different salinity regimes in different areas may influence habitat conditions and the community of fish occurring (Ghosh *et al.* 2011).

There were 10 species that were caught and they belonged to 4 families namely: *Cichlidae*, *Centrarchidae*, *Cyprinidae* and *Clariidae* (Table 1). *Cichlidae* had the highest overall percentage while *Centrarchidae* was the lowest similar to previous findings (Oyugi, 2012). The Lake Naivasha had all these fish species namely: *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Oreochromis leucostictus*, *Coptodon zillii* (Gervais, 1848), *Micropterus salmoides*, *Clarius gariepinus*, *Clarius aepithecus*, *Barbus amphigramma*, *Cyprinus carpio* var. and *Cyprinus*

Carpio Specularis. while the Lake Oloiden had only 5 species (post-its merging with Lake Naivasha). All the species tallied with those previously found in the Lake Naivasha (Nzioka *et al.* 2017). The main catch composition in the Lake Naivasha has been: *Cyprinus carpio*, *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Oreochromis leucostictus* and *Clarias gariepinus*; concurrent to previous findings (Njiru *et al.* 2017).

Crescent and Malewa had the highest number of species that were caught (7). Oseria had 5 fish species while Korongo's and Midlake's were 4. The sheltered sites/sites with edges had a higher number of fish species that were caught in comparison to the open water (Midlake). Also, the edge sites had acacia trees (*Acacia xanthophloe*) that fell into the water post water level rise: may diversify habitat. They increasing decaying matter: an ecological significance; since *Oreochromis niloticus* adapts and exploits niches available; reducing niche competition (Njiru *et al.*, 2004). *Barbus amphigramma* was not distributed throughout the Lake Naivasha as previous (Aloo *et al.* 2013). *Cyprinus Carpio* was the second in abundance as compared to the contribution of *Coptodon zillii* (Gervais, 1848) and *Micropterus salmoides*; that use visual aid to feed and are gravel spawners. Previous studies have shown that the increase in benthic feeders (*Cyprinus carpio*) increased turbidity the turbidity leading to their reduction ((Ndungu, 2014)

Lake Oloiden's catch included: *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Clarius gariepinus* and *Cyprinus Carpio Specularis*. It had fewer number of fish species as compared to the Lake Naivasha. The species that were present in the Lake Oloiden migrated from Lake Naivasha and had to adjusted to the higher salinity level (Albaret *et al.* 2004; Nyangau 2021). In Oseria 5 fish species were caught, Oloiden ST1 had 4 fish species that were caught: while Oloiden ST2 had 3 species. Oseria and Oloiden ST2 had variation in the number of fish caught; which could be associated with non-linearity in an estuary (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). The fish present in Oloiden ST2 and Oseria sites had the ability to withstand fluctuations in salinity because it was estuarine while Oloiden ST1's had to withstand a higher salinity (Albaret *et al.* 2004). *Cyprinus carpio* was found to withstand low salinity, since it was found in the transitional water (Ghosh *et al.* 2011).

Oreochromis niloticus contributed the highest percentage in the catches in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden (Table 2) (Nyangau, 2021). It was followed by *C.yprinus carpio* (16.8%) and *Clarius gariepinus* (12.3%). *Oreochromis leucostictus* contributed 2.66% while *Micropterus*

salmoides had its contribution as 1.12%. The rest of the species namely: leather carp, mirror carp, *Coptodon zillii* (Gervais, 1848), *Barbus amphigramma* and *Clarius aepithecus* had a low percentage contribution to the catch. *Oreochromis niloticus* was the highest percentage in the catch at all the study sites; able to withstand salinity fluctuations (Albaret *et al.* 2004); it was followed by *Cyprinus carpio* contrary to Nyangau 2021.

The species; *Oreochromis niloticus*' percentage was highest in Oloiden ST2, followed by Midlake, Oloiden ST1, Korongo, Crescent, Oseria then Malewa. Its high abundance in an estuarine environment could be due to high productivity; since its planktivorous and the possibility it could be a good nursery ground (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). *Cyprinus carpio*'s percentage was high in Oseria, followed by Malewa, Midlake, Korongo and Crescent while it was lowest in Oloiden ST2 and ST1. Its high abundance in Oseria could be attributed to presence of other fish; its piscivorous (Oyugi, 2012).

Clarius gariepinus was present in 4 sites: highest in Malewa, Crescent, Oloiden ST1 and it was lowest in percentage in Oloiden ST2. *Clarius aepithecus* was present in low percentages in the Oloiden ST1 (higher salinity) and Malewa (lower salinity). Catfish can withstand an estuarine environment: its anadromous fish. It may be migrating for spawning in River Malewa; since this is where it was caught in the highest percentage (Tran *et al.* 2019).

There was a low percentage of *Micropterus salmoides* that was present at Crescent and Oseria (Lake Naivasha): contrary to previous findings, it was not present only in rock bottomed site (Crescent) (Aloo *et al.* 2013). The leather carp was only present in Malewa (Lake Naivasha). Mirror carp was present in Oloiden ST1, Korongo and Midlake; its presence in a high saline environment shows it withstands salinity fluctuations (Ghosh *et al.* 2011). *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Cyprinus carpio* *specularis*, *Micropterus salmoides*, *Oreochromis leucostictus*, *Clarius gariepinus* and *Clarius aepithecus* are salinity tolerant in comparison to *Coptodon zillii* (Gervais, 1848), *Barbus amphigramma* and *Cyprinus carpio* Var. For a species to live in an estuarine environment; they must possess the ability to adjust to salinity which affects their distribution. Salinity may be a determinant in estuarine fish ecology and distribution (Ghosh *et al.* 2011). There was variation in the fish species along the salinity gradient (Albaret *et al.* 2004).

The Shannon-Wiener index was low (Figure 3): although, the highest was in Malewa, followed by Oloiden ST1 while the lowest was in Midlake. Oloiden ST1' H'; showing a good adaptability to Lake Oloiden (Gain *et al.* 2008). It was higher in Oloiden ST1 as compared to Oloiden ST2. Oseria's fish species diversity was higher than that of Oloiden ST2; there may be variability in an estuary (Albaret *et al.* 2004; Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). The species evenness was highest in Malewa, it was followed by the Midlake and Oseria while Oloiden ST1 was the lowest (Figure 4). Oloiden ST1 and ST2 had similar fish species evenness. Oloiden ST2's evenness was lower as compared to Oseria. The fish species evenness decreased with the increase in salinity. Species diversity and evenness did not exhibit linear change in the estuarine environment (Telesh and Khelebivich 2010). The low fish diversity and evenness was in contrast with Hussan *et al.* 2020.

The fish species richness was highest in Crescent and lowest in the Midlake. Oloiden ST1 was higher than Oloiden ST2 while Oseria's species richness was higher than Oloiden ST2. The result was contrary to the findings of Hussan *et al.* 2020. Oseria and Oloiden ST2 were estuarine; may experience spatial and dynamic species richness and the species present must have wide tolerance to fluctuating conditions that affect their distribution (Albaret *et al.* 2004). Salinity may influence feeding and breeding areas; aspects that affect distribution and abundance (Okyere 2018).

5.0 Conclusion and recommendation

There was a variation in the spatial diversity and distribution of fish along the salinity gradient. Some fish species of commercial importance migrated to the Lake Oloiden post its merging to Lake Naivasha. Fish species diversity and evenness were low while species richness was high. There should be further research on the fish species diversity along the salinity gradient due to changes that may occur in biotic and abiotic factors.

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